

Bifunctional Amorphous Transition-Metal Phospho-Boride Electrocatalysts for Selective Alkaline Seawater Splitting at a Current Density of 2 A cm^{-2}

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Hydrogen production by direct seawater electrolysis is an alternative technology to conventional freshwater electrolysis, mainly owing to the vast abundance of seawater reserves on earth. However, the lack of robust, active, and selective electrocatalysts that can withstand the harsh and corrosive saline conditions of seawater greatly hinders its industrial viability. Herein, a series of amorphous transition-metal phospho-borides, namely Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B are prepared by simple chemical reduction method and screened for overall alkaline seawater electrolysis. Co-P-B is found to be the best of the lot, requiring low overpotentials of $\approx 270\text{ mV}$ for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), $\approx 410\text{ mV}$ for oxygen evolution reaction (OER), and an overall voltage of 2.50 V to reach a current density of 2 A cm^{-2} in highly alkaline natural seawater. Furthermore, the optimized electrocatalyst shows formidable stability after 10,000 cycles and 30 h of chronoamperometric measurements in alkaline natural seawater without any chlorine evolution, even at higher current densities. A detailed understanding of not only HER and OER but also chlorine evolution reaction (CIER) on the Co-P-B surface is obtained by computational analysis, which also sheds light on the selectivity and stability of the catalyst at high current densities.

To ensure carbon neutrality of the whole process, intermittent energy sources like solar, wind, and hydropower are used as input energy sources to power the water electrolyzer units.^[2] Despite the promise, several challenges hinder up-scaling water electrolyzer units up to the terawatt scale. The most critical challenge is related to the electrode materials. For instance, in proton-exchange membrane water electrolyzers, only expensive (and rare) platinum-group metals (PGMs) can be used while alkaline water electrolyzers use Ni-based electrodes that are relatively less efficient. Over the years, numerous low-cost transition metal-based electrocatalysts like borides,^[3] selenides,^[4] oxides,^[5] sulfides,^[6] phosphides,^[7] carbides,^[8] and layered double hydroxides^[9] have been reported as promising alternatives with superior activity and stability. With notable advancements in electrode materials, another key bottleneck in the global

1. Introduction

Green hydrogen (H_2) production through water electrolysis is one of the most practically relevant technologies to meet the challenges implementing H_2 fuel for the growing energy demands.^[1]

implementation of water electrolyzers is the use of ultra-purified water feeds that demand the development of large-scale purification plants and eventually increase the cost and carbon footprint of the whole process. Moreover, 80% of the world's population is likely to experience a freshwater shortage, especially in arid desert

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zones, which significantly limits the deployment of conventional water electrolyzer systems in these regions.^[10]

On the other hand, direct seawater electrolysis is a more favorable option as 96.5% of the earth's surface is covered by water resources. In addition, the hydrogen generated from seawater splitting can produce fresh drinking water as a by-product.^[11] However, there are several challenges associated with seawater electrolysis in comparison with freshwater electrolysis. For instance, at low pH, chlorine evolution reaction (CLER) precedes oxygen evolution reaction (OER) due to its better kinetics, forming the corrosive Cl₂ gas. Theoretical calculations suggest that in alkaline conditions (pH > 8), the difference between the potentials for water oxidation and chloride ion oxidation (for hypochlorite formation) is ≈ 480 mV, which offers a relatively wider potential window to selectively perform OER.^[12–14] Thus, the recent research trend is based on developing electrocatalysts that can produce a sufficient amount of hydrogen with an overpotential < 480 mV by alkaline seawater electrolysis. Nevertheless, this constrains the use of these electrocatalysts at high current density for up-scaling the technology. Moreover, alkaline seawater presents its challenges, such as the precipitation of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions to form milky white precipitates of Ca(OH)₂ and Mg(OH)₂, respectively, that can deposit and block the active sites of the electrodes. In addition to these issues, seawater possesses microbes, bacteria, and other organic compounds that cause electrode poisoning and corrosion, resulting in poor stability.^[12] Thus, for the industrial breakthrough, it is required to develop an electrocatalyst with not only favorable activity and selectivity but also considerable corrosion resistance at high current densities. Especially, in an anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer (AEMWE) with zero-gap assembly, the current density can range from 500 to 2000 mA cm⁻² when operated under high alkaline conditions and elevated temperature (50–80 °C).

Over the years, electrocatalysts based on transition metals, namely Ni, Fe, and Co have mostly been studied for seawater electrolysis due to their large abundance and low cost.^[15–22] Among these, transition metal borides,^[23] phosphides,^[24] nitrides,^[25] and double-layered oxides^[26] have grabbed the attention of researchers due to their superior activity, long-term stability, and OER selectivity in alkaline seawater. Few electrocatalysts like Ni-SN@C,^[27] Ni₂P-Fe₂P,^[28] C-Co₂P,^[24] NiCoP/ NiCo-LDH,^[29] and Fe/F-Ni₂P@NC^[30] have outperformed the best reported PGM electrocatalysts. However, most of these electrocatalysts have been reported for either HER or OER, but there are not many results with bifunctional electrocatalysts for alkaline seawater electrolysis. Amongst the reported ones, very few show considerable performance and stability, and even fewer reports are made on electrocatalysts that can sustain alkaline seawater electrolysis at commercially relevant high current densities (2 A cm²). Moreover, as computational tools are gaining more prowess in advancing our understanding of interfacial reaction mechanisms, there are only a few computational studies focused on emulating the chloride chemistry occurring during seawater electrolysis. Hence, there is a dire need to incorporate computational studies on CLER as an integral part of experimental work on alkaline seawater electrolysis to gain unprecedented insights, as achieved in this work.

Previously, amorphous cobalt phospho-boride (Co-P-B) was reported as a bifunctional catalyst for alkaline freshwater elec-

trolysis with considerably good performance.^[7] Taking a cue, in this work, we develop a series of amorphous transition-metal phospho-borides (TMPBs) such as Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B, and experimentally screen the best-performing candidates for alkaline seawater electrolysis. Amongst the screened ones, an optimized composition of Co-P-B demonstrates the best bifunctional activity in alkaline simulated as well as alkaline natural seawater. Detailed investigations into the material's properties were performed to identify the differences between the three catalysts. Being the best catalyst, Co-P-B was probed in greater detail to establish its selectivity and stability in alkaline natural seawater at an ultrahigh current density of 2 A cm⁻². Later, computational models were used to simulate amorphous Co-P-B structure and identify the possible catalytically active sites. Finally, HER, OER, and CLER reaction mechanisms were simulated over the optimized Co-P-B structures to further extend our current understanding of the catalyst surfaces under seawater-like conditions. The present work not only reports Co a robust catalyst as a promising candidate for industrial seawater splitting but also presents a new understanding of the competing OER and CLER over the catalyst surface through computational modeling, which will prove to be exemplary in the coming times.

2. Results and Discussion

To simplify the catalyst optimization process for the series of TMPBs, the molar ratio of B and P was first optimized for Co-P-B and then implemented directly to Ni-P-B and Fe-P-B. For Co-P-B, the B/P molar ratios were varied as 1, 3, 5, and 7. Based on their electrochemical activity (overpotential recorded at 10 mA cm⁻² (η_{10})), the optimal ratio was found to be B/P = 5 (henceforth denoted as Co-P-B) for both HER and OER (Figure S1, Supporting Information). Considering this optimized ratio, Ni-P-B and Fe-P-B catalysts with a B/P molar ratio of 5 were synthesized and compared with Co-P-B. The physical characterization measurements were also limited to Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B electrocatalysts. SEM and TEM images of Co-P-B (Figure 1a,d) and Ni-P-B (Figure 1b,e) show particle-like morphology with an average particle size of 46 ± 2 nm (Figure S2, Supporting Information) and 51 ± 2 nm (Figure S3, Supporting Information), respectively. All the spherical particles in Co-P-B and Ni-P-B are interconnected, with gaps in between them to form a porous structure (Figure S4, Supporting Information). On the contrary, Fe-P-B (Figure 1c,f; Figure S4, Supporting Information) showed 2D nanoflakes-like morphology. The SAED pattern (inset of Figure 1d,f) and HR-TEM images (Figure S6a, Supporting Information) for Co-P-B displayed diffused rings and lack of crystallinity, suggesting a completely amorphous structure which is also endorsed by the absence of any peak in the XRD pattern (Figure S5, Supporting Information). On the contrary, a broad peak centered at 45° is noticed in the XRD pattern of Ni-P-B (Figure S5, Supporting Information), which is in good agreement with the SAED pattern showing distinct diffraction spots in the rings (inset of Figure 1e). Interestingly, Fe-P-B shows weak diffraction spots in the SAED pattern despite no signature of crystallinity in XRD pattern, hinting at its local short-range ordering. Thus, Co-P-B is completely amorphous while a small degree of crystallinity exists in Ni-P-B and Fe-P-B. The uniform distribution of elements present within the catalyst powder is illustrated by elemental mapping

Figure 1. a–c) SEM image, d–f) TEM micrograph with inset showing SAED pattern of Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B, respectively.

(Figures S7–S9, Supporting Information). The existence of O and C in the sample can be due to ex-situ measurements performed on all catalysts.

The surface chemical states of the electrocatalysts were investigated using XPS (Figure 2) and the survey scans (Figure S10, Supporting Information) confirm the presence of all the key elements in the samples. For Co-P-B, Co 2p level was deconvoluted

to multiple peaks with a binding energy (BE) at 777.7 eV corresponding to elemental cobalt (Co^0) (Figure 2a), and at 780.6 eV and 782.9 eV attributed to trivalent (Co^{3+}) and divalent (Co^{2+}) cobalt oxide, respectively. A negative shift of 0.4 eV is detected in the BE for the Co^0 peak in Co-P-B as compared to pure metallic cobalt (778.1 eV), implying higher electron density on the cobalt sites. This electron enrichment is observed only in the Co-P-B

Figure 2. XPS spectra of a) Co 2p, b) Ni 2p, c) Fe 2p; d) B 1s, e) P 2p levels and N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm of f) Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B catalysts.

sample containing both P and B as no such shift is usually observed for the Co⁰ peak in Co-B and Co-P.^[7] The presence of oxidized cobalt is attributed to ex-situ catalyst preparation and its exposure to the ambient atmosphere during the transfer of the catalyst to the measurement chamber. The satellite peaks are also observed for Co 2p_{3/2} at the higher BE of 786.3 and 788.8 eV, corresponding to oxidized cobalt. A similar set of peaks for elemental and oxidized cobalt are deconvoluted in Co 2p_{1/2} levels. XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} (Figure 2b) in Ni-P-B show that Ni also exists in both elemental (Ni⁰) and oxidized states (Ni²⁺) with BE peak at 852.4 and 856.1 eV, respectively, and a corresponding satellite peak of oxide noticed at 861.6 eV. The higher BE peaks at 869.4 and 873.8 eV are assigned to both these Ni species in the Ni 2p_{1/2} level. On the contrary, Fe was found to be only in the oxidized state (Fe²⁺) with a corresponding peak at 711.5 eV in Fe 2p_{3/2} and 725.1 eV in Fe 2p_{1/2} with the related satellite peaks at 720.0 and 733.2 eV, respectively (Figure 2c). Co-P-B and Ni-P-B display elemental boron (B⁰) peaks at 187.9 and 187.6 eV in the B1s level (Figure 2d), respectively. In comparison to pure boron with BE 187.1 eV, a positive shift of 0.8 and 0.5 eV was observed in B⁰ peaks for Co-P-B and Ni-P-B, respectively, indicating a partial loss of electron density from boron to metal sites. This effect is more dominant in the case of Co-P-B based on the higher BE shift. In contrast, Fe-P-B did not exhibit any B⁰ peak, instead only an oxidized boron (B₂O₃) peak was observed at a higher BE range of 191.9 eV. This oxidized boron is also detected in Co and Ni counterparts with peaks at 191.4 eV and 191.6 eV, respectively. Similarly, for the P 2p state (Figure 2e), the P⁰ peaks at 129.9 and 129.6 eV are visible only in the case of Co-P-B and Ni-P-B with oxidized peaks (133.7, 133.4 and 133.2 eV) existing in all the three TMPB catalysts. As the surface composition of P in Fe-P-B is a mere 0.52 at% (Table S1, Supporting Information), only a tiny peak at 133.2 eV is seen while the relatively smaller peak at 129.0 eV cannot be detected. Unlike the case of boron, the P⁰ peak shows a negative shift of 0.3 and 0.6 eV in the BE value for Co-P-B and Ni-P-B, in comparison to pure phosphorous (130.2 eV). This negative shift in the BE value indicates the enrichment of electrons on the P site as a result of the ensemble effect.^[7,31] This unique behavior of electron transfer from B to the metal site and then to P is commonly noticed in the case of amorphous TMPBs, which has been confirmed experimentally and theoretically from previous studies.^[3,7,32–34] This exclusive mechanism modulates the optimal electron density on the metal sites making them more active for overall water-splitting reaction.

The physical surface area of the catalysts was determined using BET^[34] analysis. As per the IUPAC classification, the N₂ adsorption and desorption curves of all three catalysts (Figure 2f) resemble the Type IV isotherm and H1-type hysteresis loop. The BET surface area of Fe-P-B (146.6 m² g⁻¹) is ~9.6 and ~7.6 times higher when compared with Ni-P-B (15.1 m² g⁻¹) and Co-P-B (19.1 m² g⁻¹), respectively. The observed higher BET surface area values agree well with the TEM images depicting a 2D flake-like structure for Fe-P-B (Figure 1c,f).^[35] In contrast, Co-P-B and Ni-P-B catalysts display a lower surface area, mainly due to the agglomeration of the nanoparticles, which is evident from the SEM images (Figure 1a,b).

The best OER and HER performance achieved with the optimized composition of B/P = 5 in the Co-P-B catalyst was attributed to the lower charge transfer resistance (Figure S11, Sup-

porting Information) and higher C_{DL} value (Figure S12, Supporting Information). The electrochemical testing of the Co-P-B electrocatalyst was repeated several times and the results were consistent (Figure S13, Supporting Information). Using this optimal ratio of B/P = 5, all three TMPB catalysts were tested in alkaline simulated seawater (ASSW) to establish their electrochemical performance (Figure 3a–h). It is noteworthy that Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ salts were also introduced in the electrolyte, resulting in milky precipitates, to better simulate the alkaline seawater environment but without biological and organic impurities. For HER, η₁₀ value (Figure 3a) recorded with Pt/C, Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B was -35, -126, -166, and -364 mV respectively. Amongst the TMPBs, Co-P-B yields the best HER activity, while Fe-P-B requires a very high overpotential suggesting the inactive surface of this catalyst. To confirm that the HER data is not influenced by Pt contamination from the counter electrode, the LSV data was repeated with graphite as the counter electrode, and the results were reproducible (Figure S14a, Supporting Information). The absence of any Pt contamination on the cathode catalyst was also confirmed by XPS measurement of the cathode catalyst after HER measurement (Figure S14b, Supporting Information). The calculated Tafel slope value of Fe-P-B (151 mV dec⁻¹) was much greater than that of Co-P-B (78 mV dec⁻¹) and Ni-P-B (77 mV dec⁻¹) (Figure 3b). Thus, it is concluded that the HER proceeds more efficiently in Co-P-B and Ni-P-B, and the reaction mechanism followed here is the Volmer Heyrovsky mechanism. The charge transfer behavior at the electrode/electrolyte interface was investigated by fitting the Nyquist plot (Figure 3c) using an equivalent circuit (inset of Figure 3c). No major variation was observed in the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), with Ni-P-B (6.7 Ω) showing a slightly higher value than Co-P-B (5.6 Ω) and Fe-P-B (5.2 Ω). Moreover, the reaction rate is also governed by the number of electrochemically active sites that are related to the double-layer capacitance. A higher C_{DL} value was observed for Ni-P-B (3.3 mF cm⁻²) and Fe-P-B (2.4 mF cm⁻²) as compared to Co-P-B (1.6 mF cm⁻²) suggesting the lowest ECSA for Co-P-B (Figure 3d; Figure S15, Supporting Information). The observed lower value of C_{DL} for Co-P-B is in contrast with its higher HER rates. This leads us to believe that the intrinsic activity of sites in Co-P-B will be relatively very high, resulting in improved HER rates. To better understand the intrinsic activity of the catalyst for HER, TOF values were calculated^[34] at an overpotential of 150 mV. The TOF value for Co-P-B (0.018114 atom⁻¹s⁻¹) is ~20 and 200 times higher than Ni-P-B (0.000948 atom⁻¹s⁻¹) and Fe-P-B (0.000089 atom⁻¹s⁻¹), respectively. Thus, the HER activity in Co-P-B is manifested by an increase in the intrinsic activity of the active sites due to the optimized electron density at Co and P sites through electronic exchange between Co, B, and P, as confirmed by XPS. This phenomenon is also established by the C_{DL} normalized LSV curve (Figure S16, Supporting Information), where Co-P-B remained the best catalyst after eliminating the effect of ECSA. Meanwhile, Co-P-B is on par with the best reported non-noble electrocatalysts in ASSW for HER (Table S2, Supporting Information). Few non-noble electrocatalysts did show lower overpotential than the present catalyst; however, all these catalysts are loaded on porous conductive Ni foam with very high catalyst loading (10–20 times more) compared to the present catalyst, which is deposited on non-porous glassy carbon. The chemical changes on the surface of the Co-P-B

Figure 3. Linear polarization curve a), Tafel plot b), Nyquist plot c) for HER. d) Plot representing the differences in cathodic and anodic current densities at different scan rates to determine the C_{DL} values. Linear polarization curve e), Tafel plot f), Nyquist plot g) for OER, h) LSV in the pre-OER potential region acquired at a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} for Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, and Fe-P-B catalyst in ASSW.

catalyst post-HER were investigated by XPS (Figure S17, Supporting Information) and Raman spectroscopy (Figure S18, Supporting Information). In the Co $2p_{3/2}$ level, a peak attributed to the oxidized phase ($\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$) of cobalt at 781.2 eV ^[31] is visible. Even B and P are detected in completely oxidized states. In alkaline electrolytes, the water molecules are reduced at the cathode surface to form OH^- ions which get adsorbed on the surface to form cobalt hydroxide.^[31] The transformation to $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ was also verified by the Raman spectra (Figure S18, Supporting Information), where after HER, new peaks emerge at 535 and 608 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$.^[36]

Recently, most of the electrocatalysts have been reported either for HER or OER, but very few can attain bifunctionality for overall alkaline seawater splitting (Table S2, Supporting Information). Here, all the three TMPBs were investigated for OER in ASSW by anodic polarization to explore their bifunctional characteristic. Figure 3e depicts the LSV curve of Co-P-B, Ni-P-B, Fe-P-B, and commercial RuO_2 with overpotential requirements of 281, 390, 422, and 379 mV for 10 mA cm^{-2} in ASSW. Even at higher current densities (100 mA cm^{-2}), Co-P-B (360 mV) shows superior activity than other electrocatalysts. Besides, all the electrocatalysts exhibit faster kinetics during the OER reaction, as indicated by the Tafel slope values (Figure 3f). In a reported comparative study,^[37] it was observed that a Tafel slope value above 100 mV dec^{-1} is obtained when M to M-OH^* formation (the first step in OER) is the rate-limiting step whereas values lower than 100 mV dec^{-1} are observed when the subsequent OER steps are rate-limiting. Based on the Tafel slope values in Figure 3f, it can be proposed that M to M-OH^* formation is not the rate-limiting step in any of the three catalysts. Moreover, all the three TMPBs exhibit similar conductivity at the interface, as indicated by their R_{ct} values (Figure 3g). Another important parameter affecting the OER activity is the formation of surface-active species ($^*\text{OH}$ and $^*\text{OOH}$) which can be investigated from the pre-oxidation peak

formation. By performing LSV at a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} , the formation of hydroxide/oxyhydroxide intermediates was investigated in the first OER cycle.^[31] Figure 3h shows the formation of CoOOH and NiOOH species at 1.29 and 1.47 V for Co-P-B and Ni-P-B, respectively, whereas Fe-P-B does not show any pre-oxidation peak. This surface oxide formation is consistent with the “precatalyst” theory claiming that metal borides and phosphides act as the precatalyst to assist in the formation of active oxyhydroxide species.^[3,7,31] The degree of oxidation on the surface is determined by the intensity of the peak. In the case of Co-P-B, the degree of oxidation is higher which means more Co sites are transformed on the surface to form CoOOH active species to facilitate the OER process. The physical evidence of CoOOH formation on the catalyst surface post-OER is provided by the evolution of two new peaks at 780.2 and 781.8 eV , assigned to $\gamma\text{-CoOOH}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ species,^[31] in Co $2p$ level of XPS spectra (Figure 4a). The BE peaks at 192.3 and 133.9 eV for B 1s (Figure 4b) and P 2p (Figure 4c) levels, respectively, illustrate that both these elements are entirely oxidized. This surface reconstruction of Co-P-B during OER was also validated through Raman spectra (Figure 4d) where the evolution of CoOOH species (502 and 594 cm^{-1}) from the partially oxidized phase (462 cm^{-1} , 511 cm^{-1} , and 666 cm^{-1}) was seen.^[36] Similar to HER, the TOF values in OER are also one order and two orders of magnitude higher for Co-P-B ($0.015886 \text{ atom}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) as compared to Ni-P-B ($0.001797 \text{ atom}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and Fe-P-B ($0.000056 \text{ atom}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$), respectively, at 300 mV. Further, to highlight the role of amorphous structure in enhancing the catalytic activity, crystalline cobalt phospho-boride (labeled as Co-P-B_{600}^*) was synthesized by annealing the as-prepared Co-P-B catalyst at 600°C under N_2 atmosphere for 2 h. The XRD pattern (Figure S19a, Supporting Information) confirmed the crystalline structure of the annealed Co-P-B_{600}^* powder with diffraction peaks that can be indexed to tetragonal Co_2B (PDF 89–1994) and monoclinic CoP_2 (PDF

Figure 4. High-resolution XPS spectra for a) Co 2p, b) B 1s and c) P 2p levels, and d) Raman spectra of Co-P-B catalyst post-OER in ASSW.

26–0481) phases, respectively.^[35,38,39] SEM images of Co-P-B₆₀₀* (Figure S19b, Supporting Information) reveal a particle-like morphology that is substantially more agglomerated than amorphous Co-P-B, which is expected due to the higher annealing temperature. On electrochemical testing, Co-P-B₆₀₀* showed η_{10} values of 242 and 345 mV for HER and OER, respectively when tested in ASSW. These values are \sim 116 and \sim 64 mV higher than that of amorphous Co-P-B catalyst for HER (Figure S20a, Supporting Information) and OER (Figure S20b, Supporting Information), respectively. The higher electrochemical rates in amorphous Co-P-B underlines the significance of amorphous structure that presents a large number of uncoordinated active sites, compared to the crystalline structure. A similar observation is also reported in past literature.^[21,40,41] Furthermore, EIS data (Figure S20c,d, Supporting Information) indicate that Co-P-B₆₀₀* has higher R_{ct} values than amorphous Co-P-B, suggesting it to be one of the factors affecting the activity of crystalline Co-P-B₆₀₀*.

So far, it has been established that Co-P-B shows commendable performance for HER and OER in alkaline simulated seawater. However, natural seawater contains not only an ample amount of dissolved cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , etc.) but also various biological and organic impurities to poison the electrode surface. Hence, the Co-P-B catalyst was investigated for its electrochemical performance in untreated alkaline natural seawater (ANSW). Under alkaline conditions, the formation of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ precipitate (milky white solid particles) was observed in natural seawater,^[12] which was similar to that observed in ASSW and was not separated during the electrochemical testing. For both HER

(Figure S21a, Supporting Information) and OER (Figure S21b, Supporting Information), a marginal increase in overpotential value was observed in ANSW which is attributed to the presence of the impurity ions in seawater. These ions can get adsorbed onto the electrode surface to increase the resistance for electron transfer, as confirmed by the Nyquist plot (Figure S22, Supporting Information), thereby increasing the overpotential required to drive the electrochemical reaction.^[2] The formation of CoOOH species during OER was confirmed by the peak in the range of 1.27–1.31 V (vs RHE) in all three alkaline electrolytes with the highest degree of oxidation (Figure S24a, Supporting Information) and C_{DL} values (Figure S24b, Supporting Information) recorded for Co-P-B in ASSW, thus supporting the lowest overpotential value registered in ASSW. The bifunctional nature of the electrocatalyst was further shown through continuous LSV sweeps from the cathodic to the anodic region in the range of -0.34 to $+1.86$ V (vs RHE). Co-P-B catalyst exhibits good bifunctionality in both ASSW and ANSW (Figure S25, Supporting Information). During the scan, a peak arises at $+0.2$ V which is due to mild oxidation on the surface, while a higher potential peak at $+1.29$ V is attributed to the transformation of the cobalt species to the higher oxidation state of CoOOH species on the surface.^[7]

Figure 5a demonstrates the results from a two-electrode setup where the Co-P-B electrocatalyst deposited on Ni foam (denoted as Co-P-B/NF) acts as both electrodes (cathode and anode). In ASSW and ANSW, the overall cell voltage required to achieve 100 mA cm^{-2} is only 1.72 V (without iR correction), whereas the combination of Pt/C || RuO_2 needed a much higher

Figure 5. a) Polarization curves in two-electrode setup for Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF catalyst deposited on Ni-foam in ASSW and ANSW, for comparison Pt || RuO₂ deposited on Ni-foam was also tested in ASSW along with bare Ni-foam. Faradaic efficiency plot of Co-P-B/NF catalyst measured in ANSW for b) HER, and c) OER. d) Tafel polarization curves of Co-P-B/NF electrocatalysts on Ni foam in ANSW.

voltage of 1.98 V. With 80% iR correction, the same current densities in ASSW and ANSW (Figure S27, Supporting Information) can be reached at a cell voltage of 1.61 V, which is well within the ~480 mV potential window between OER and chloride oxidation. Furthermore, the two-electrode system with Co-P-B/NF catalyst was also operated using a single AA battery of 1.5 V in ASSW, without MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ to avoid the solution turning milky so the bubbles could be visibly seen. Indeed, the bubble generation was evident on both electrodes at this minimal applied voltage (Video in Supporting Information). Finally, to understand its OER selectivity over other chloride oxidation reactions, Faradaic efficiency measurement, and o-tolidine tests were performed. Using a Hoffmann apparatus, the Faradaic efficiency was evaluated at a current density of 50 mA cm⁻² in ANSW. Co-P-B/NF exhibited ~99% efficiency for both HER (Figure 5b) and OER (Figure 5c), indicating the absence of chloride oxidation. For further confirmation, o-tolidine tests were performed to examine the presence of chloride ions in the electrolyte after the long-term stability test in the ANSW solution (without MgCl₂ and CaCl₂).^[42,43] The known quantity of electrolytes was collected after 15 h of continuous tests at 1.8 V and added to the testing solution. The resulting electrolyte did not show any visible change in color confirming the absence of any traceable amount of hypochlorite ions, which was further validated by the UV-Vis spectra (Figure S26, Supporting Information). Therefore, the above results confirm the OER selectivity of Co-P-B over chloride oxidation reactions in ANSW.

To substantiate the corrosion-resistant properties of Co-P-B/NF in ANSW (Figure 5d), the Tafel polarization curve

and associated corrosion parameters for all the samples were calculated.^[44] The corrosion potential (E_{corr}) typically provides insights into the electrode surface condition towards corrosion tolerance in the electrolyte, while I_{corr} represents the corrosion kinetics within the system.^[45] Notably, the corrosion resistance of the as-prepared Co-P-B/NF electrode ($E_{\text{corr}} = 0.52$ V, $I_{\text{corr}} = 1.10 \times 10^{-4}$ A) significantly surpasses that of the bare NF electrode ($E_{\text{corr}} = 0.13$ V, $I_{\text{corr}} = 2.33 \times 10^{-3}$ A). Furthermore, a significant increase in corrosion resistance was noticed for Co-P-B after HER ($E_{\text{corr}} = 0.87$ V, $I_{\text{corr}} = 1.51 \times 10^{-6}$ A) and OER ($E_{\text{corr}} = 0.75$ V, $I_{\text{corr}} = 2.96 \times 10^{-8}$ A) processes. This enhancement in corrosion resistance after HER and OER can be attributed to the presence of oxidized boride, as confirmed by XPS spectra, forming a protective layer that shields the surface from corrosion in ANSW!^[44,46,47] Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the Co-P-B electrocatalyst is highly active, selective, and robust in natural seawater. As a result, it can be considered a reliable option for further optimization toward industrial implementation.

To replicate the conditions inside a seawater-driven alkaline electrolyzer operating at high current densities, the Co-P-B/NF electrocatalyst was tested in harsh and highly alkaline untreated seawater (6 M KOH + seawater). Figure 6a depicts Co-P-B/NF catalysts requiring very low overpotentials of 265 mV (586 mV) and 400 mV (685 mV) for HER and OER, respectively with 80% iR correction (without iR correction) to achieve a large current density of 2 A cm⁻². The OER overpotential of the Co-P-B/NF to achieve this high current density is less than 480 mV (required to trigger chloride oxidation), suggesting that selective OER will take place.

Figure 6. a) Linear polarization curves in HER and OER of Co-P-B/NF without and with 80% iR correction. b) Polarization curves of Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF for overall seawater splitting in 6 M KOH + seawater (without iR correction). c) Multi-step chronoamperometric test of Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF in 6 M KOH + seawater. d) o-tolidine test for the evolution of hypochlorite: UV-Vis spectra of the testing solutions after the addition of 5.96 μmol of NaOCl, 10 mL of 6 M KOH + seawater electrolyte collected after 10,000 cycles, multi-step chronoamperometric test, and 30 h stability test, and inset showing the photographs of the testing solutions after addition of electrolyte. e) Chronoamperometric plot of Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF maintained at a constant potential of 1.82 V (vs RHE) for 30 h.

Moreover, the overpotential values of HER and OER are lower than the reported non-precious electrocatalysts in ANSW at such high current densities.^[43,48–51] Considering the superior catalytic performance of the Co-P-B/NF electrocatalyst, further investigation was performed by integrating the catalysts in a two-electrode assembly using alkaline seawater (6 M KOH + seawater). Notably, the Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF system (Figure 6b) required an overall cell voltage of 2.11 V and 2.50 V (without iR correction) to reach current densities of 1 and 2 A cm^{-2} , respectively. These outstanding results are highly encouraging as it will certainly re-

quire less than 2.5 V to reach the maximum operating current density of 2 A cm^{-2} when used in a real AEMWE, where solution resistance will be minimal owing to the zero-gap assembly. A slight negligible decrement (2.6 V at 2 A cm^{-2}) in the activity was observed after 10,000 cycles (Figure 6b) which might be due to the small amount of impurities covering the surface of the electrode and thus blocking the surface active sites for seawater electrolysis. The long-term durability of electrodes operating at industrially relevant current densities (above 200 mA cm^{-2}) is crucial for practical application. Thus, the stability test for

Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF system was performed at a considerably high current density of 230 mA cm⁻² in 6 M KOH + seawater electrolyte. A commendable stability was observed with a marginal degradation of ~10% (~25 mA cm⁻²) in current density over 30 h (Figure 6e). Under the same conditions, a bare Ni foam substrate shows a rapid decline in the current densities, confirming the stable nature of the surface Co-P-B/NF coating. After the stability test, the LSV curves (Figure S28, Supporting Information) showed a trivial decrease in performance at high current density, demonstrating its robustness for large-scale applications. As it is highly desirable to develop electrolyzers working under fluctuating and highly intermittent renewable energy devices, finally a multi-step chronoamperometric test (Figure 6c) was carried out for the Co-P-B/NF || Co-P-B/NF electrodes to assess their ability to consistently generate stable currents under dynamic power supply. The result illustrates that in the whole test range (0.2 to 2 A cm⁻²), the current density remained highly stable, rising to the highest voltage of 2.5 V and declining to the lowest voltage of 1.75 V (without iR correction). Even after undergoing a rigorous multi-step stability test at a higher current density, the catalysts maintain their initial potential with no noticeable degradation in LSV (Figure 6b). In the o-tolidine test (Figure 6d), there is no evidence of chloride oxidation products detected in the electrolyte, even after subjecting it to 10,000 cycles, a multi-step chronoamperometric test, and 30 h stability test. This confirms that the sole reaction occurring on the anode surface is the OER. These results reveal that the Co-P-B/NF electrode maintains its selective, efficient, and resilient characteristics under industrial conditions for alkaline seawater splitting.

In amorphous systems, the identification of catalytically active centers is much more challenging as compared to crystalline structures. To understand the reasons for the higher performance of amorphous Co-P-B and obtain further insight into the catalyst sites, theoretical investigations were conducted with the aid of molecular dynamics (MD) simulation by constructing amorphous models (Figure 7a) of Co-P-B and Co-B (as a reference). Further details regarding the MD simulations are provided in ESI. In our previous report,^[52] the threefold (TF-2CoB) site in Co-B (Figure 7b) was discovered to be the most active site for both half-reactions and thus this site was preferred to investigate the catalytic activity to understand the role played by substitutional replacement of B with P. To account for the effect of different B/P ratios in Co-P-B, two different P concentrations were considered by substituting B atoms with single P or double P atoms simultaneously in the amorphous Co-B cluster. Based on the positions of the replaced B atoms near the threefold site, several structures were obtained containing single P atoms (designated as Co-P-B_M models) (Figure S29, Supporting Information) and double P atoms (designated as Co-2P-B_M models) (Figure S30, Supporting Information).

Radial distribution function (RDF) $g(r)$ was plotted to verify the amorphous nature of the simulated models (Figure S31, Supporting Information). Non-zero $g(r)$ in long-range and the absence of sharp peaks confirm the amorphous nature of Co-B, Co-P-B_M, and Co-2P-B_M. Here, the major contribution was due to the Co-B bond with peaks at 2.08 Å, while Co-Co and B-B bonds also contribute with peaks at 2.58 Å and a shoulder peak at 1.79 Å, respectively. These peaks indicate the 1:1 stoichiometric ratio of Co and B in Co-B with short-range order formed by Co-B, Co-Co, and B-B

bonds. All the Co-P-B_M and Co-2P-B_M models show good agreement with the Co-B model but show a slight shift in Co-B and B-B peaks, inferring the expansion of the bonds, which might be due to the inclusion of P atoms in the Co-B structure. Thus, the simulated structures of Co-P-B_M and Co-2P-B_M are fair representations of the experimentally synthesized amorphous catalysts.

There have not been many insightful computational studies that model the CLER and hence there is a dearth of knowledge about the actual selective mechanism in saline water electrolytes. To explore the kinetic competition, CLER was also studied along with the conventional OER and HER on the catalyst models, and the overpotentials were calculated for each reaction. Upon investigation of OER activity at different sites on Co-B, it was found that the Co₁ atom of the TF-2CoB site was the best site for OER with the lowest overpotential and the most optimum Gibbs free energy for each reaction intermediate. Thus, only the Co₁ atom was selected as a preferred site for calculating overpotential values in all Co-B, Co-P-B_M, and Co-2P-B_M models. The change in Gibbs free energy for the rate-limiting step (RLS) and the corresponding overpotential value for all the reactions are summarized in Table S3 (Supporting Information). Of all the considered cases, direct-Co-P-B containing single P atoms (Figure 7c) and 2Co_direct-Co-2P-B containing double P atoms (Figure 7d) have shown the best improvement toward OER activity as compared to Co-B. Hereafter, these two cases will be referred to as Co-P-B and Co-2P-B, respectively, until specified otherwise.

For OER, the Gibbs free energy diagram of Co-B, Co-P-B, and Co-2P-B at $U = 0$ V and $U = 1.23$ V (thermodynamic potential) are presented in Figure 7e,f respectively. As speculated from the Tafel plot (Figure 3f), the first OER step takes place rather efficiently in Co-P-B. For all three structures, M-O to M-OOH is the RLS for OER at the thermodynamic potential. In the case of Co-P-B_M models (Figure S32, Supporting Information), only when B is directly substituted by P at the TF-2CoB site, a reduction in OER overpotential was observed ($\eta = 0.85$ V). This scenario is completely different for the Co-2P-B_M models (Figure S33, Supporting Information), where except for one case, the overpotential value decreases as compared to Co-B, with the lowest overpotential of 0.72 V. When ANSW is used as an electrolyte, the difference between the oxidation potentials for OER and CLER is small and due to its simpler kinetics, CLER is usually favored. Thus, to design a catalyst with good OER selectivity in seawater, it should not only have a lower OER overpotential but simultaneously have a much higher CLER overpotential. Thus, OER and CLER overpotentials as well as the difference between them were calculated for all the computed models (Table S3, Supporting Information). The RLS for CLER was found to be the desorption of chlorine molecules from the catalyst. All the amorphous metal phospho-boride models showed higher overpotentials for CLER than OER, indicating that they are more selective towards OER. Moreover, Co-2P-B showed ~100 and ~450 mV higher overpotential difference between CLER and OER than that shown by Co-B and RuO₂,^[53,54] respectively, suggesting it to be highly OER selective, which is also manifested from the experimental data.

On comparing the computed overpotential values at different sites with those in Co-B, it was observed that the sites in Co-P-B_M models that are active for OER are less active for HER. A similar phenomenon was reported in our recent article where amorphous Co-W-B^[52] catalyst presented complementing sites

Figure 7. a) Amorphous cluster of Co-B with 64 atoms, b) Shows a top view of the few atomic layers with various possible P substitutions at the B site near the TF-2CoB site, c) direct_Co-P-B containing single P atoms (Co-P-B), and d) 2Co_direct_Co-2P-B containing double P atoms (Co-2P-B). Here, blue, green, and yellow atoms correspond to Co, B, and P respectively. Gibbs free energy diagram for OER of Co-B, Co-P-B, and Co-2P-B at e) $U = 0$ V and f) $U = 1.23$ V, Overpotential plot for g) OER, h) CIER, and i) HER for the best sites in Co-B, Co-P-B, and Co-2P-B amorphous structures. Here M represents the catalyst surface.

that were more active either for HER or OER. On the contrary, Co-2P-B_M models possess sites that are equally active for both HER and OER, though the most active HER and OER sites are different. This proves that Co-P-B with a specific B/P ratio plays a promoting role for both the half-reactions, highlighting the bifunctional nature as observed experimentally. Figure 7g–i present the overpotential plots for the most active sites in Co-B, Co-P-B, and Co-2P-B for HER, OER, and CIER respectively. For HER, the calculated overpotentials for Co-P-B and Co-2P-B are higher than that of Pt (0.09 V), which matches well with the experimental value.

Löwdin charge analysis (on atoms in the 2TF-CoB site) was performed for all the Co-B, Co-P-B_M, and Co-2P-B_M models. Table S4 (Supporting Information) reports the charge over each atom in the 2TF-2CoB site along with the difference in charge as compared to Co-B. For both Co-P-B_M and Co-2P-B_M models, all OER and HER active sites are enriched with electrons on the Co₁ and Co₂ sites. This accumulation of charges at the active sites is due to charge depletion from B atoms of catalyst within the interior part of the cluster, as also suggested by the XPS spectra. Apart from Löwdin charge analysis, the ELF plot (Figure 8) also shows a systematic increment in electron localization over Co₁ as the

Figure 8. Comparative analysis of Electron localization function (ELF) between a) Co-B b) Co-P-B and c) Co-2P-B.

concentration of P increases near the threefold active site. The incorporation of P at the direct threefold site provides an electron-rich environment ensuring the accumulation of charges over the Co_1 atom. As M-O to M-OOH is the RLS during the OER, the O^* species binds relatively strongly with Co_1 in the case of the Co-B catalyst. However, upon introducing P, the excess charge on Co_1 weakens the bond strength between O^* -Co due to coulomb repulsion making it an optimum interaction to facilitate the OER by reducing the overpotential value. The electron enrichment on Co_1 was higher for the Co-2P-B than Co-P-B, thus making that site relatively more electronegative to reduce the binding strength of O^* species over Co_1 . Similarly, for HER, the Co_1 site with electron enrichment suits well for the H-adsorption and H_2 desorption from the surface. The above computational analyses are in good agreement with the experimental findings where an optimal B/P ratio achieves the best OER and HER activity. On the other hand, the electron enrichment on the Co site due to B and P, as noticed from XPS, is also visible theoretically in the various models. These sites are well suited for both half-reactions making Co-P-B a bifunctional catalyst. Also, the increase in the overpotential difference between ClER and OER explains the selective nature of the Co-P-B catalyst for alkaline seawater splitting.

3. Conclusion

In summary, amorphous transition metal phospho-borides prepared by a facile chemical reduction method demonstrated high catalytic activity and stability for overall alkaline seawater splitting. Amongst the synthesized series of TMPBs, Co-P-B displayed significantly higher intrinsic activity, making it the most favorable catalyst for electrolysis. Based on the experimental and theoretical analysis, the enhancement in the electrochemical activity following the addition of P into Co-B was proven, which eventually facilitates the water splitting. Though alkaline simulated seawater provided the most ideal environment for Co-P-B, electrochemical activity in alkaline natural seawater was also quite comparable. Remarkably, in a two-electrode assembly, $\text{Co-P-B/NF}^{\text{HER}} \parallel \text{Co-P-B/NF}^{\text{OER}}$ demonstrated a low cell voltage of 2.50 V for 2 A cm^{-2} in alkaline natural seawater. Most importantly, the electrocatalyst showed a minor loss in activity during 10,000 cycles of reusability test, dynamic chronoamperometric test, and 30 h of stability test. Co-P-B/NF showed 99% Faradaic ef-

iciency and selectivity for OER over chloride oxidation products in alkaline natural seawater. Computational studies identified the most active sites in the Co-P-B amorphous cluster and also simulated the HER, OER, and ClER mechanisms over these sites to calculate the rate-limiting steps and reaction overpotentials. A synergy between the experimental and computational data was obtained for further understanding of such amorphous catalysts that can serve as cost-effective building blocks for realizing alkaline seawater-based electrolyzers commercially.

4. Experimental Section

Reagents Used: Cobalt chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, Researchlab), sodium hypophosphite ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, Researchlab), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , 98%, Researchlab), nickel chloride hexahydrate ($\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, Researchlab), ferric nitrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%, Research lab), potassium hydroxide pellets (KOH, 99%, Researchlab), sodium chloride (NaCl, 99.5%, Researchlab), magnesium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%, Researchlab), anhydrous calcium chloride (CaCl_2 , 95%, Researchlab), o-tolidine solution, and sodium hypochlorite solution (NaOCl, Researchlab) were used. Deionized (DI) water was used as the general-purpose solvent. The seawater used in this study was collected from the Arabian Sea.

Synthesis of Electrocatalyst Powder: A facile chemical reduction method was used to synthesize a series of amorphous TMPB electrocatalysts. For Co-P-B, a mixture of cobalt chloride ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05 M) and sodium hypophosphite (NaH_2PO_2) was dispersed in 31 mL of deionized water and stirred for 15 min. Later, sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) was added as a boron source and reducing agent to the mixture and kept under continuous stirring for 20 min until the bubbles ceased. For all the experiments, the molar ratio of (B+P)/Co was kept thrice to ensure the complete reduction of metal ions. The obtained black precipitate was washed with deionized water and ethanol several times to remove the undesirable impurities and existing by-products.^[7,34] The molar concentrations of NaBH_4 and NaH_2PO_2 were varied to optimize the B/P ratio in the catalyst. Similarly, Ni-P-B and Fe-P-B were synthesized using nickel chloride and ferric nitrate as metal precursors, respectively.

Materials Characterizations: The surface morphology and the particle size distribution of the catalyst were detected using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (JEOL-SEM JSM 7001F) and transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEOL 2100F Cs-corrected). Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) were used to identify the crystalline nature and the elemental presence of the catalysts, respectively. Using a powder X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku-mini flex, $\text{Cu K}\alpha = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), the structure profile of the catalyst was recorded in the 2θ range of 5° to 90° . The elemental compositions and chemical states

of the catalysts were established using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (PHI Versa Probe III, AlK_{α} (1486.6 eV)). By maintaining the C 1 s spectrum as the reference, the binding energy of each element was calibrated. Micro-Raman spectroscopy was performed on a Renishaw machine using a laser excitation wavelength of 532 nm. The physical surface area of the powder catalyst was detected by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET, Micro-metric 3-flex 3500 gas sorption analyzer) technique using the N_2 adsorption method with the multipoint surface analyzer. The catalyst powder was pre-treated at 125 °C for 3 h to remove the moisture content from the catalyst powders before measuring the surface area.

Electrochemical Measurements: In order to test the electrochemical activity of the powder catalysts, a homogeneous catalyst ink was prepared by dispersing 5 mg of catalyst powder into 1 mL of ethanol and ultrasonicated for 2 min. Separately, a binder solution was prepared by adding 40 μ L of Nafion to 1 mL of ethanol and homogenized in an ultrasonic bath for \sim 15 s. Prior to catalyst deposition, 10 μ L of Nafion binder solution was deposited on the surface of a polished glassy carbon electrode (GCE, diameter 3 mm) using a drop-casting method. As soon as the binder dries up, 20 μ L of catalyst ink was deposited, achieving a catalyst loading of 1.4 mg cm^{-2} . All the electrochemical measurements were performed using a three-electrode setup with a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as a reference, Pt or graphite as a counter, and catalyst-deposited GCE as a working electrode. A potentiostat system (CH instrument, CH16011E) was used for all the electrochemical measurements. The measurements were performed using three different electrolytes, namely 1 M KOH (alkaline water, AW), 1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl + 0.05 M $MgCl_2$ + 0.01 M $CaCl_2$ (alkaline simulated seawater, ASSW), and natural seawater + 1 M KOH (alkaline natural seawater, ANSW). The linear polarization curves for HER and OER were recorded in the range of -1.4 V to -1.06 V (vs SCE) and 0 V to 0.8 V (vs SCE), respectively, at a scan rate of 10 mV s^{-1} . Prior to HER tests, a constant potential (-0.34 V vs RHE) was applied for \sim 15 min to pre-condition the catalyst surface and remove the surface oxides and inhomogeneities, if any, achieving a steady-state value. After the measurements, all the potential values were converted to a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) by adding $+1.06$ V, calculated from Nernst equation $E = E^0 + 0.059 \cdot pH$, where $E^0 = 0.241$ V for SCE. Before the linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) tests, chronoamperometry measurements were performed until a steady-state current was reached. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was recorded in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 1 Hz for OER and HER at $+1.6$ V and -0.3 V (vs RHE), respectively. The values for charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and solution resistance (R_s) were obtained by fitting the semicircle in the Nyquist plot by Randles circuit (two resistances and a capacitance), and the R_s value was 100% compensated for iR losses. The plot of $\log(i)$ against overpotential was linearly fitted to obtain Tafel slope values. The electrochemical surface area (ECSA) was investigated from the double-layer capacitance (C_{DL}) values using cyclic voltammetry (CV) scans performed in the non-Faradaic regions. Different scan rates (40, 60, 80, 100, and 120 mV s^{-1}) were used to acquire these CV curves within the range of ± 100 mV of the open circuit potential. To determine the C_{DL} values, the slope was obtained by linearly fitting the plot of the scan rates versus differences in cathodic and anodic current densities. Turnover frequency (TOF) was determined using the calculations reported by Popczun et al.^[55] The bifunctional nature of the catalyst was evaluated by measuring LSV at a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} from -0.34 to 1.86 V (vs RHE).

To replicate the electrodes used in a commercial AEMWE assembly, the Co-P-B catalyst was deposited on a Ni foam substrate (5 x 10 x 0.5 mm). Prior to the deposition, the Ni foam was thoroughly cleaned with acetone, NaOH solution, and 10 wt.% HCl separately and finally dried under an IR lamp. The drop-casting method was used to deposit 0.14 mL of Nafion binder solution and 0.28 mL of the catalyst ink on the surface of the Ni foam, which was then dried under an IR lamp. The overall seawater splitting was determined in a two-electrode assembly by using Co-P-B-coated Ni foam as both electrodes. The polarization curves at high current density (2 A cm^{-2}), recyclability behavior for 10,000 linear polarization sweeps, chronoamperometric measurement at 230 mA cm^{-2} for 30 h, and multi-step chronoamperometric test ranging from 0.2 to 2 A cm^{-2} were investigated with this two-electrode assembly using 6 M KOH + seawater as the electrolyte. The corrosion resistance behavior of the Co-P-B

catalyst on Ni foam was also established in ANSW using a three-electrode configuration.

OER Selectivity: To detect any traces of ClO^- (hypochlorite) formed during alkaline seawater electrolysis, the o-tolidine test was conducted by using a testing solution of 0.5 mL of o-tolidine mixed with 10 mL of DI water. To calibrate, NaOCl of known concentrations (5.96, 11.92, 23.85, and 29.82 μ mol) was added to the testing solution, and the corresponding peak intensity at 425 nm was analyzed in the UV-visible spectra. Later, 0.2 mL of each electrolyte (ANSW), collected after the stability test for 30 h, multi-step chronoamperometric test, and recyclability test, was added into the testing solution to identify any color changes through UV-vis spectra due to the presence of ClO^- .^[43] Hoffman apparatus was utilized to measure the Faradaic efficiency for both HER and OER using Co-P-B-coated Ni foam as electrodes. Prior to the measurements, a constant current was applied for 30 min to condition the electrode surface and remove atmospheric gases from the apparatus. The volume of gases (H_2 and O_2) produced on each side of the electrodes was measured and compared with the theoretically calculated values of H_2 and O_2 gas to calculate the Faradic efficiency.^[23]

Computational Details: Electronic properties and catalytic activities toward HER, OER, and ClER for amorphous Co-B and Co-P-B were studied using the QUANTUM ESPRESSO^[56] code within the framework of density functional theory (DFT). All the calculations were performed using PBE (Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof) exchange-correlation functional as part of generalized gradient approximation (GGA).^[57] All structural optimization and electronic properties were performed with a plane wave cutoff of 60 Ry and a charge density cutoff of 600 Ry with ultrasoft pseudopotential. Crystalline CoB structure was initially used as a starting input for molecular dynamics (MD) simulation using Car-Parrinello dynamics^[58,59] to prepare amorphous Co-B. Further details regarding MD simulation are mentioned in the supplementary information. To investigate the surface-active sites, 15 Å of vacuum was given in one of the directions to consider this system as slab restricting any electronic interaction with its periodic image. Structural relaxation and electronic properties were calculated using a Γ -centered k-mesh grid of $4 \times 4 \times 1$ and $8 \times 8 \times 1$, respectively. All the Co-P-B models were studied for HER, OER, and ClER by the adsorption of suitable intermediates.^[60] In this method, the Gibbs free energy of each intermediate was calculated to determine the overpotential and rate-determining step of the reaction. Further details of the reaction mechanism and calculation of Gibbs free energy are provided in the supplementary information.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

hydrogen evolution reaction, non-noble catalysts, overall water-splitting, oxygen evolution reaction, Seawater electrolysis, transition-metal phospho borides

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